

Fertilizer management — inorganic sources

Effect of Zn on grain yield and Zn uptake by lowland rice in South Gujarat

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One-fourth of South Gujarat rice soils have Zn deficiency (less than 0.60 mg kg⁻¹ DTPA-extractable Zn). Another 39%, classified as medium-deficient (0.6-1.0 mg kg⁻¹ DTPA-extractable Zn), will probably worsen from continuous waterlogging of ricefields. Presently, a blanket application of 2 kg Zn ha⁻¹ is recommended but considered insufficient for low Zn soils.

We examined the effect of 0, 5.6, 11.2, and 16.8 kg Zn ha⁻¹ on Jaya (coarse grain variety) and GR.11 (fine grain variety) in field experiments during 1992 and 1993 monsoon seasons. The experiments were conducted in a randomized block design with four replications in plots of 6.0- × 3.0- m on Vertic Ustochrept soils. Chemical analysis showed that the soil was low in DTPA-extractable Zn (0.60 mg kg⁻¹) and alkaline KMnO₄-extractable N (230 kg ha⁻¹), medium in Olsen P (12.4 kg ha⁻¹) and high in neutral N NH₄O Ac-extractable K (283 kg ha⁻¹) with a pH of 7.9 without problems of salinity or sodicity. Nitrogen was applied at 100 kg ha⁻¹ and P at 22 kg ha⁻¹. The entire amount of Zn (as ZnSO₄·7H₂O), P, and 40 kg N were applied before puddling. The remaining N was applied in two equal splits each after 20 and 45 d of transplanting. The sources of N and P were diammonium phosphate (DAP) and urea. The crop was irrigated during drought periods. At harvest, diacid extracts of grain and straw samples were analyzed for Zn using an AA spectrophotometer.

Pooled analysis on grain yield and total Zn uptake data indicated nonsignificant first- and second-order inter-

2. Relationship between Zn level and total Zn uptake.

actions between Zn levels, years, and varieties. In main effects, only the Zn levels were significant for yield and uptake. A quadratic relationship was found between Zn levels and pooled yield and pooled total Zn uptake (Figs. 1 and 2). Solving the equation

$$X_{(opt)} = \frac{-b}{2c}$$

where $X_{(opt)}$ = optimum Zn dose for uptake, indicated a continuation of Zn uptake up to 14.3 kg Zn ha⁻¹ and a yield increase up to 13.6 kg Zn ha⁻¹. Solving the equation,

$$X_{(e)} = \frac{1}{2c} \left(-\frac{q}{p} - b \right)$$

where $X_{(e)}$ = dose of Zn for economic yield, q = cost of Zn at Rs 54.76 kg⁻¹, p = price of rice at Rs 4500 t⁻¹, indicated an economic dose of 11.9 kg Zn ha⁻¹. Thus the present recommendation of 2 kg Zn ha⁻¹ is inadequate for rice production in Zn-deficient lowland soils of South Gujarat. Our results using these two rice varieties indicate the need to increase Zn application to about 12 kg ha⁻¹ for these soils. ■

Optimization of potassium application in acid soils of Tamil Nadu

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To assess the response of K in Typic Ustropepts soils (pH 5.6; EC 0.24 dS m⁻¹) and to optimize its application for low-land irrigated rice (37.3 kg available K ha⁻¹), we laid out a trial of variety ASD18 on 3.4- × 4.5-m plots with 15- × 10-cm hill spacing during the 1995 dry season (June-September) with six levels of K₂O and two levels of lime (as CaO) using a factorial randomized

Table 1. Influence of K on grain yield of rice in acid soils.

K ₂ O (kg ha ⁻¹)	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)		
	L0 ^a	L1	Mean
0	4.6	5.1	4.8
25	4.7	5.2	5.0
50	4.9	5.5	5.2
75	5.1	6.5	5.8
100	5.3	6.1	5.7
125	5.5	6.0	5.8
CD (p=0.05)			
Potash	0.09		
Lime	0.11		
Potash × lime	0.28		

^aL0 = zero lime, L1 = lime at 2.8 t ha⁻¹.